

Some Polymeric Nickel(II) Complexes of Acetophenone Semicarbazone

VIJAY K. ARORA, K. B. PANDEYA and R. P. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007, India

Manuscript received 18 January 1979, accepted 27 April 1979

Ni(II) complexes of acetophenone semicarbazone have been described. Complexes $\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})\text{X}_2$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{CH}_3\text{COO}, 1/2\text{SO}_4$) show subnormal magnetic moments (2.6-2.7 BM) and $\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ shows normal magnetic moment (3.01 BM). Polymeric structures involving ligand- and anion-bridges have been suggested. Visible spectra of all the complexes contain one broad absorption band at $\sim 16000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Infrared spectra show apsc acting as bidentate ligand coordinating through oxygen and hydrazinic nitrogen.

SEVERAL nickel(II) complexes have been found to have polymeric structures. For $\text{Ni}(\text{en})_2\text{Cl}_2$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{en})_2\text{Br}_2$, dimeric octahedral molecules with halogen bridges have been reported¹. The structure of nickel(II) acetyl acetonate² consists of trimeric molecules in which the nickel atoms reach the octahedral coordination by sharing oxygen atoms. Nickel(II) ethylthiolate have been reported³ to consist of cyclic hexamers with sulphur bridges in which nickel atoms have square-planar coordination. Several nickel(II) complexes are also formed by infinite chains with various ligands bridging nickel atoms⁴⁻⁶. The present paper describes nickel(II) complexes of acetophenone semicarbazone (apsc)[I]. All the complexes prepared appear to be polymeric involving ligand- and anion-bridges.

Experimental

Preparation of the Ligand: Aqueous solutions of semicarbazide hydrochloride (0.1 mole) and sodium acetate (0.1 mole) were mixed together. To this solution, 0.1 mole of acetophenone (Analar) was

mixed. The contents were shaken vigorously. White coloured acetophenone semicarbazone separated out. It was filtered, washed with distilled water and recrystallised from ethanol.

Preparation of Complexes: Ethanolic solution of ligand and hot aquo-ethanolic solutions of the hydrated metal salts were mixed in the molar ratio of 1 : 1 and the contents were refluxed for 4 to 5 hours. Green to blue coloured complex precipitated out in each case. It was filtered, washed with 50% ethanol and dried in an electric oven at $\sim 60^\circ$.

Physical Measurements: Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made by Gouy method using mercury(II) tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) as calibrating agent ($\chi_g = 16.44 \times 10^6$ cgs units). Electronic spectra of complexes were recorded in nujol mull on a Russian C-10 automatic recording spectrophotometer. I.R. spectra ($4000-700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer-137 automatic recording spectrophotometer and far infra-red ($4000-200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) on Perkin-Elmer 621 in KBr.

Results and Discussion

Composition of complexes are given in Table 1. Except for $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{apsc})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ all other complexes have general composition $\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})\text{X}_2$, where $\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{CH}_3\text{COO}, 1/2\text{SO}_4$. It may be mentioned

TABLE I—COLOUR AND COMPOSITION OF NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES OF ACETOPHENONE SEMICARBAZONE(apsc)

Compound	Colour	%M	Analytical data, found (calculated)		
			%C	%H	%N
apsc	White	—	61.05, (61.01)	6.20, (6.21)	23.70, (23.72)
$\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})\text{Cl}_2$	Sea-green	19.16, (19.18)	35.01, (35.21)	3.57, (3.58)	13.61, (13.69)
$\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})\text{Br}_2$	Parrot-green	14.56, (14.90)	27.23, (27.43)	2.70, (2.79)	10.61, (10.66)
$\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Light-blue	16.22, (16.00)	32.45, (32.55)	3.32, (3.31)	12.60, (12.66)
$\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	Light-blue	16.57, (16.64)	30.60, (30.53)	3.17, (3.10)	11.75, (11.87)
$\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Sea-green	9.94, (10.2)	45.61, (45.50)	4.65, (4.63)	17.62, (17.69)

that 1 : 1 metal : ligand composition is obtained, even when the preparations were carried out with 2 moles (or even higher) of ligand per mole of metal ion. With semicarbazide⁷ and several semicarbazones, ScCR_1R_2 ($\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{Me}$, $\text{R}_1\text{R}_2 = \text{heptanone}$, $\text{R}_1 = \text{Me}$, $\text{R}_2 = \text{butyl}$), nickel(II) complexes are reported to have composition NiL_2X_2 ($\text{X} = \text{Cl, Br}$).

Magnetic moments of the $\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})\text{X}_2$ complexes in the present studies lie in the range 2.6-2.7 BM. Subnormal magnetic moment values are indicative of polymeric structure of the complexes leading to antiferromagnetic exchange interactions. Low solubility of the complexes is in support of polymeric structures. The magnetic properties of polynuclear complexes are governed by the extent of the direct metal-metal interaction. If the overlap of the d -orbitals from the two neighbouring metal ions is insignificant, no M-M bonding may be formed and the subnormal magnetic moment values are observed only at low temperatures⁸. But the subnormal magnetic moment values at room temperature, as observed in the complexes under discussion, are suggestive of strong metal-metal interaction. It is interesting to compare the present situation with those obtained in the similar complexes of semicarbazide⁹ and semicarbazones¹⁰, where the magnetic moment data indicate the overlap of the orbitals to be comparatively less significant. Visible spectra (Fig. 2) of all the complexes show a broad band with maximum at $\sim 16000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Table 2) assignable to the transition ${}^3\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F})(\nu_a)$ for a six coordinate tetragonal complex. The transitions ${}^3\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$, ${}^3\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$, expected to lie at $\sim 9000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 26000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, could not be recorded because of limitations with the spectrophotometer used.

Infrared bands for acetophenone semicarbazone and the nickel(II) complexes are listed in Table 3.

Fig. 2. Visible spectra of
A. $\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})\text{Cl}_2$ (IN NUJOL)
B. $\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ (IN NUJOL)
C. $\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (IN NUJOL)
D. $\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (IN NUJOL)
E. $\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})\text{Br}_2$ (IN NUJOL)

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND VISIBLE SPECTRAL BANDS FOR NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES OF ACETOPHENONE SEMICARBAZONE (apsc)

Complex	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Spectral bands cm^{-1}
$\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})\text{Cl}_2$	2.65	15300
$\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})\text{Br}_2$	2.64	16000
$\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	2.59	16000
$\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	2.72	15900
$\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	3.01	15600

TABLE 3—INFRARED SPECTRAL BANDS (cm^{-1}) FOR ACETOPHENONE SEMICARBAZONE (apsc) AND ITS NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES

Ligand	$\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})\text{Cl}_2$	$\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})\text{Br}_2$	$\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	$\text{Ni}(\text{apsc})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Assignments
3571(s)	3448(s)	3338(vs)	3508(sh)	3460(vs)	3448(sh)	$\nu \text{C-H}$
3174(vs)	3225(vs)		3278(vs)	3350(sh)	3333(vs)	$\nu \text{N-H}$
3000(w)				3250(sh)	3174(sh)	
1739(vs)	1650(m)	1650(b,s)	1630(vs,b)	1625(vs,b)	1640(vs)	$\nu \text{C-O}$
1574(vs)	1635(vs)	1625(s)	1595(m)	1595(sh)	1540(s)	$\delta(\text{NH}_2)$ and Amide I
1470(sh)	1625(s)	1535(m)		1565(sh)		
	1540(vs)					
1428(vs)	1400(b,s)		1410(s)	1418(vs)	1385(vs)	mainly
1298(vs)	1215(s)	1215(m)	1270(s)	1278(s)	1210(sh)	$\nu \text{C-N} + \delta(\text{NH})$ Amide II
1123(s)	1149(b,s)	1135(s)	1160	1111(b,s)	1140(b,s)	$\nu \text{C-N} + \delta(\text{NH}_2)$ Amide III
1069(m)			1090(s)	1069(sh)		$\delta(\text{NH}_2)$
1020(m)			1050	1020(sh)		
			970			
917(m)				913(m)	825	$\delta(\text{O=C-N})$
775(vs)			730(m)		765(m)	$\nu(\text{O=C-N}_2)$
757(vs)						
689(vs)						

ν →very strong, s→strong, (b,s)→broad and strong, m→medium, w→weak, sh→shoulder.

The ligand spectrum contains characteristic bands¹¹ for ν_{C-H} , ν_{N-H} , $\nu_{C=O}$, δ_{N-H} and ν_{C-N} . A band at 3571 cm^{-1} is assigned to unbonded ν_{N-H} and a complex series of bands between 3370 cm^{-1} and 3000 cm^{-1} are assignable to bonded ν_{N-H} and ν_{C-H} modes. Band at 1739 cm^{-1} is characteristic absorption of carbonyl group, whereas bands at 1574 cm^{-1} and 1470 cm^{-1} are assignable to δ_{NH_2} and amide I coupled with each other. A very strong band at 1428 cm^{-1} is mainly due to $(\nu_{C-N} + \delta_{NH})$ and is so-called amide(II) band of secondary amine considered by Fraser and Price¹² to be out of phase combination of O-C-N and N-H vibration modes. The corresponding in-phase mode primarily the C-N stretching is the strong band at 1298 cm^{-1} and is so-called amide(III) which in fact is a combination of $(\nu_{C-N} + \delta_{NH_2})$. In the region ranging from 1150-1000 cm^{-1} , there are three bands at 1123 cm^{-1} , 1069 cm^{-1} and 1020 cm^{-1} assignable to δ_{NH_2} . A strong band at 917 cm^{-1} is due to $\delta_{(O-C-N)}$ and a group of bands at 775, 757, 689 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\pi_{(O=C-N_2)}$ in accordance with Campbell *et al*⁹. Spectra of the complexes contain most of these bands and the bands corresponding to anions, in addition. Changes in the ligand bands suggest bidentate nature of the ligand coordinating through oxygen and hydrazinic nitrogen atom. Definite lowering in the positions of $\nu_{C=O}$ and ν_{C-N} bands are observed. The $\delta_{(O=C-N)}$ and $\pi_{(O=C-N_2)}$ bands of the ligand are absent in the spectra of the complexes.

Ni(apsc)Cl₂ and *Ni(apsc)Br₂*: Both the complexes show subnormal magnetic moment values, 2.65 and 2.64 BM respectively. A polymeric structure has, therefore, been inferred. Keeping in view, the composition of the complexes, the polymeric structure (Fig. 1a) may be suggested. An infinite chain of dihalobridged NiX₂ units making square-plane of halide ions about Ni(II) are presumed and the acetophenone semicarbazone molecule is taken to link neighbouring Ni(II) ions. A similar structure has been suggested for corresponding Cu(II) complexes of thiosemicarbazide¹³ and for some diazine complexes¹⁴ of Cu(II). For a diazolato complex¹⁵ of Cu(II) chloride such a structure has been confirmed by X-ray determination. Infrared evidence for the bridging halo groups which appear in region (250-150 cm^{-1})¹⁶ could not be provided as the region below 200 cm^{-1} was not covered in the range of instrument used. But the absence of terminal halogen group is evident as no ir band for $\nu_{(Ni-X)}$ terminal is observed. Where the terminal-stretching bands appear in region 400-200 cm^{-1} for M-Cl and 300-200 cm^{-1} for M-Br.

Ni(apsc)(CH₃COO)₂: As discussed earlier the subnormal magnetic moment value (2.72 BM) suggests polymeric structure for the complex. The structure (Fig. 1b) is tentatively proposed. The $\nu_{a(COO^-)}$ and $\nu_{s(COO^-)}$ of free acetate ion^{16(a)} are observed at 1560 and 1416 cm^{-1} respectively. The separation between the two $\nu_{(C-O)}$ is much larger

Fig 1 (a) Where X=Cl, Br
O-N=APSC

Fig.1(d) O-N=APSC

Fig.1(c) O-N=APSC

Fig.1(b). O-N=APSC

in unidentate complexes than in the free ion. In the case of bidentate complexes, separation between the two frequencies is smaller than in the free ion, however two $\nu_{(C-O)}$ are close to the free ion values in the bridging complex. This is, what has been observed in this complex. The two $\nu_{a(COO^-)}$ and $\nu_{s(COO^-)}$ of complexed acetate ion are 1565 cm^{-1} and 1410 cm^{-1} . There are complications, however, due to $(\delta_{NH_2} + A_{amide I})$ and $(\nu_{C-N} + \delta_{NH})$ of the ligand lying in the same region.

Ni(apsc)SO₄·2H₂O: Infrared spectrum of the complex suggests that SO₄ group is present in bidentate coordination. Intense bands at 1160, 1090 and 1050 cm^{-1} may be readily assigned as components of ν_s and the band at 970 cm^{-1} to ν_1 of the sulphato group^{16(b)}. The observed frequencies favour the bridging mode of the sulphato group. Infrared spectrum also shows bands for the coordinated water in this complex. Antisymmetric and symmetric OH stretching bands^{16(c)} which occur at 3550-3200 cm^{-1} are mixed up with the ν_{N-H} bands. The HOH bending^{16(d)} known to

lie in the range $1630-1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is observed at 1600 cm^{-1} . In addition, a rocking mode^{16(c)} of coordinated water at 730 cm^{-1} is observed in the spectrum of complex under discussion. Based on above information, the polymeric structure is in support of the subnormal magnetic moment 2.59 BM of the complex [Fig. 1(c)].

$Ni(\text{apsc})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Only this compound contains two apsc molecules per metal ion. The complex shows magnetic moment of 3.01 BM . IR spectrum of the complex suggests that NO_3 group is present as a free ion. The absorption band^{16(d)} at 700 cm^{-1} is assignable to ν_4 , at 1385 cm^{-1} to ν_3 and at 825 cm^{-1} to ν_2 . The absorption band due to ν_1 is absent, confirming that NO_3 group is uncoordinated. This is further supported by the nonsplit nature of ν_3 and ν_4 . IR spectrum of the complex also shows bands for coordinated water. Antisymmetric and symmetric OH stretching^{16(d)} which occur at $3550-3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are mixed up with $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ band and thus HOH bending^{16(c)} is observed at 1620 cm^{-1} . In addition, rocking mode^{16(d)} of coordinated water is observed at 765 cm^{-1} .

Although a six-coordinate monomeric structure may be possible for this complex with two bidentate apsc molecules giving in-plane coordination and the two water molecules occupying axial positions, we intend to propose a ligand-bridged polymeric structure [Fig. 1(d)] in view of low solubility of the complex.

Normal magnetic moment value for the complex (3.01 BM) suggests that the proposed polymeric structure does not lead to significant overlap of d -orbitals. Several examples of this type are known in literature^{17,18}.

Acknowledgement

This work was done under the UGC research project "Coordination Chemistry of Trace Elements

in Human Body". The authors are grateful to the University Grants Commission, New Delhi, for the financial assistance.

References

1. A. S. ANTSYVSHKINA and M. A. PORAI-KOSHITS, *Kohl. Akad. Nauk, SSSR*, 1962, **143**, 105.
2. G. J. BULLEN, R. MASON and P. PAULING, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 456.
3. P. WOODWARD, L. F. DAHL, E. W. ABEL and B. C. CROSSE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 5251.
4. F. D. AYRES, P. PAULING and G. B. ROBERTSON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **3**, 1303.
5. M. G. B. DREW, D. M. L. GOODGAME, M. A. HITCHMAN and D. ROGERS, *Chem. Commun.*, 1965, 477.
6. G. N. TISHCHENKO, Tr. Inst Kristallography, *Akad. Nauk, SSSR*, 1955, **11**, 93.
7. B. BEECROFT, M. J. M. CAMPBELL and R. GRZEŃKOWIAK, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 55.
8. R. L. CARLIN, "Transition Metal Chemistry", 1970, **6**, 19, Marcel Dekker Ltd. Publication, New York.
9. M. J. M. CAMPBELL and R. GRZEŃKOWIAK, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 1865.
10. M. J. M. CAMPBELL and R. GRZEŃKOWIAK, *Inorg. Nuclear Chem. Letters*, 1969, **5**, 27.
11. W. H. T. DAVISON and P. E. CHIRSTIE, *Chem. Abs.*, 1955, 3389.
12. R. D. B. FRASER and W. C. PRICE, *Proc. Royal Soc.*, 1953, **66**, 1410.
13. M. J. M. CAMPBELL and R. GRZEŃKOWIAK, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)* 1967, 396.
14. E. REIMANN and G. GORDON, *Nature*, 1965, **205**, 902.
15. J. A. J. JARVIS, *Acta Cryst.*, 1962, **15**, 964.
16. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley-Interscience, a Division of John-Wiley & Sons, New York, III Edition, 1978, p. 317, 16(a)—p. 232, 16(b)—p. 239, 16(c)—p. 227 and 16(d)—p. 220.
17. M. INOUE, M. KISHITA and M. KUBO, *Acta Cryst.*, 1963, **16**, 699; *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **3**, 239.